

TALENT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AMONG IT SECTOR EMPLOYEES

R. Sangeetha* & Dr. K. Rajakarthyayan**

* Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Vellalar College for Women (Autonomous), Thindal, Erode, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor & Head, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Erode Arts and Science College, Erode, Tamilnadu

Abstract:

The talent management is the basic tool in 21st century of human assets management. As Information and Technology (IT) industry play a vital role in the country's economic growth, it is important to ensure the smoothness operations so that long-term growth and development can be achieved with fewer obstacles. Hence, a constant availability of a large pool of talented and experienced people is crucial to carry out functions. However, employee turnover issue is a critical phenomenon within IT industry globally and locally. To curb this issue, academic attentions have diverted the focus upon the implementation of talent management practices on both employee engagement and employee retention. The present paper seeks to identify the common problems faced by the IT sector employees. For the accomplishment of this objective, data were collected from 100 IT Sector employees working with the help of self structured questionnaire. The results of the study highlighted that managers don't give importance to develop the employee's capabilities and their career growth which in turn leads to talent attrition in IT Sector in India.

Key Words: Talent Management, Problems, IT Sector & Employees

Introduction:

India has the world largest pool of highly qualified technical graduates making it as a most preferred destination for outsourcing and most lucrative sector for investments. However when we talk about the attrition rate, IT Sector is on the top in the list, which affect the organization adversely. The attrition rate is higher in junior level of employees which would be up to 30 percent in coming times whereas in middle level management would witness 20 percent attrition rate. The attrition rate would be lowest in top management employees Times of India (2014).

The human capital has become the key factor in determining the success of any organization. "Human talent-the combined capacity and will of people to achieve an organisation's goal – is a productive resource like no other. Talent management is a process and needs integrative approach, pervading all aspects related to the human capital of the organization, right from acquisition to development and retention. The current research is focussed on the study of telecom sector. It is the largest revenue generator and also a major creator of jobs. The competition in this sector is high and hence in order to sustain, these organizations need robust talent management system.

Top 5 IT Companies:

The Indian IT Industry is a fast growing industry in India and it has shown a phenomenal growth in the last few decades. The Indian IT Industry is contributing significantly to economic growth of the nation and is expanding swiftly with the passage of time.

1. Tata Consultancy Services (TCS): When it's about IT Companies in India, Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) stand on the top and was started way back in the year 1968.

Presently, it has numerous projects of domestic as well as international organizations. TCS provides various services that include Assurance Services, Business Processing Services, Social Computing, Business Intelligence, etc.

Market Capitalization: Rs 4,46,006 Crore (As on 16th January 2016)

2. Infosys: Infosys is one of the fastest growing IT Companies in India and its consolidated revenue grew by 6.4% during the financial year 2014-15. Multiple Award Winner, Infosys was incorporated in the year 1981 and since its inception; the company has continuously provided quality rich products and services to its clients. Infosys offers a diverse range of services that include Management Consulting, Business Process Outsourcing, Software Testing, Engineering Services, Business Applications, etc. Hospitality, Retail, Communication, Education and Insurance are some of the industries in which Infosys offer its services.

Market Capitalization: Rs 2,61,897 Crore (As on 16th January 2016)

3. Wipro: Wipro offers numerous services that include Cloud Management Service, Human Resource Outsourcing, Data Integration, Testing Service, etc. Some of the sectors in which Wipro offers its services include Manufacturing, Banking, Automotive, Retail and Transportation. Wipro is ranked 3rd in the list of top 10 best IT companies in India. Founded in the year 1945, Wipro is a leading IT company in India with operations in 6 continents across the world.

Market Capitalization: Rs 1,34,257 Crore (As on 16th January 2016)

4. HCL Technologies: Next on this list is HCL Technologies, a known name in the Indian IT Industry. Founded in the year 1976, HCL Technologies offers its services to various sectors that include Government Organization, Electronics, Telecom, Retail, Manufacturing; etc. Headquartered in Noida, Uttar Pradesh, HCL Technologies has operations in more than 25 countries across the world. Some of the services offered by HCL Technologies are Cloud Computing, Network Services, Business Process Outsourcing and Testing Services.

Market Capitalization: Rs 1,18,051 Crore (As on 16th January 2016)

5. Tech Mahindra: Winner of Porter Prize, Tech Mahindra was founded in the year 1986 and presently operates in more than 50 countries across the world. Talking about services, Tech Mahindra offers a wide range of services that include Software Testing, Network Services, Web Content Management, Business Applications, etc. Tech Mahindra offers its services to the sectors like Hospitality, Banking, Telecom, Insurance, Retail, etc.

Market Capitalization: Rs 50,299 Crore (As on 16th January 2016)

Talent Management Practices:

The talent management practices that were common in many industries were recruitment and selection, succession planning, Training and development, performance management, compensation, employee retention and senior management involvement. Apart from the above mentioned practices few more practices that are practiced in many industries include Alignment with business goals, embeddedness in culture etc. the above mentioned practices

Broader Classification of Talent Management Practices Talent management is more than a process for giving feedback and providing coaching/ training. When appropriate practices are used, it becomes a powerful tool for helping employees develop further and achieve their full potential.

Activities and Work Process of Talent Management:

Talent management, when handled strategically, flows from the organization's mission, vision, values, and goals. This enables every employee to see where he or she fits within the organization.

Talent management includes the following activities and work processes.

- ✓ Develop clear job descriptions so you know the skills, abilities, and experience needed from a new employee.
- ✓ Select appropriate employees who have superior potential and fit your organization's culture, with an appropriate selection process.
- ✓ Negotiate requirements and accomplishment-based performance standards, outcomes, and measures within a performance development planning system.
- ✓ Provide effective employee on boarding and ongoing training and development opportunities that reflect both the employee's and the organization's needs.
- ✓ Provide on-going coaching, mentoring, and feedback so the employee feels valued and important.

- ✓ Conduct quarterly performance development planning discussions that focus on the employee's interests for career development.

Review of Literature:

M. Dhanabhakyaam and K. Kokilambal (2014) the paper titled “A Study On Existing Talent Management Practice And Its Benefits Across Industries“ this paper aims to bring out talent management practices which are adopted in four major industries Banking, Healthcare, Manufacturing and IT industry. And also practices which are more common among different industries. This research aims to map the existing talent management practices and its benefits to an individual or an organization.

Dr. Usha Tiwari and Devanshi shrivastava (2013) the paper titled “strategies and practices of talent management and their impact on employee retention and effectiveness“ the study revealed that age of employees is independent from satisfaction but experience of employees does affect the satisfaction with the practices of talent management. Finding of ANOVA revealed that each of the parameter has a different impact on effectiveness of talent management practices but a distinctive impact on employee's satisfaction. In relation to the workplace, talent is described as the personal qualities “of those individuals who can make a difference to organizational performance either through their immediate contribution or, in the longer-term, by demonstrating the highest levels of potential” (CIPD, 2012). Today’s talented employees have much greater expectations of the developmental and psychological rewards they get from their work and it is no longer sufficient to offer high salaries alone (UK commission for Employment & Skills, 2012).

Objectives:

- The following are the objectives of the study
- ✓ To identify the socio-economic profile of the respondents.
- ✓ To evaluate the common problems faced by the employees of selected IT sector.

Research Methodology:

The basic objective of the study is to explore the major problems faced by the select IT sector employees with effective implementation of talent management practices which will help the management in improving their talent management system so that the organization would complete more effectively in the present competitive business world. The study was descriptive in nature was used to identify the problems of select IT sector companies. The study is mainly based on the primary data and secondary data. The primary data has been collected by issuing well structured questionnaire to 100 employees working in the IT sector. The secondary data is collected from the magazines, websites, etc. from the general public.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The socio-economic profile of the respondents has been evaluated by using simple percentage analysis and the results are summarized in the following table shown below.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile of the Sample Respondents

S.No	Variable	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	21-25 Years	45	45
		26-30 Years	35	35
		Above 31 Years	20	20
2.	Gender	Male	60	60
		Female	40	40

3.	Marital status	Married	35	35
		Unmarried	65	65
4.	Designation	Mid Level Employee	35	35
		Entry Level Employee	65	65
5.	Total Experiences	Below 1 Year	25	25
		1- 3 Years	45	45
		Above 3 Years	30	30

Source: Primary Data

From the above table is identified that most of the respondents belong to the age group of 21-25 years. 60 Percent of the respondents are male.65 percent of the respondents are unmarried. Most of the respondents 65 percent are at the entry level employee. 45 percent of the respondents have 1- 3 years if their total experience.

Table 2: Problems faced by the employees

S.No	Problems	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5
1.	The managers don't spent enough time with the employees to solve their problems.	07	13	15	38	15
2.	On the job training programme are not inadequate.	12	17	42	12	10
3.	Benefits and appraisal are not up to the mark.	15	45	17	25	15
4.	Mangers don't give importance to the development of employee's capabilities and their career growth.	55	12	13	10	25
5.	Poor interaction and co-operation with other departments.	10	13	13	15	35

Source: Primary Data

The above table says that rank 1 is given to the problem 4 managers don't give importance to the development of employee's capabilities and their career growth. Rank 2 is given to the Problem 3 Benefits and appraisal are not up to the mark, rank 3 is given to the problem 2 On the job training programme are not inadequate, rank 4 is given to the problem 1 The managers don't spent enough time with the employees to solve their problems and finally rank 5 is given to the problem 5 Poor interaction and co-operation with other departments.

Findings:

The following are the findings of the study

- ✓ Majority of the respondents belong to the age group of 21-25 years.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are male.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are unmarried.
- ✓ Majority of the respondent's designation is at entry level employee.
- ✓ Majority of the respondent's total experience is 1- 3 years.

Suggestions:

The suggestions which can be made at this juncture are:

- ✓ Organisation must have meaningful capabilities (skills, behaviours, abilities and knowledge) required throughout the organisation.
- ✓ Organisations must be able to relate the skills and capabilities to a role of demand, such as a job position, project or leadership role.
- ✓ Talent management processes must create a comprehensive profile of their people - employees, contractors, or Candidates.
- ✓ Most certified training should be given to the employee to boost their effectiveness and efficiency. It should be used as a tool of motivation.

Conclusion:

The companies invest in talent management practices but it is not seen across all the companies in the IT sector. There is need to formalize the talent management systems in organization. Although employees are satisfied with the prevailing Talent management practices, there is scope of improvement. The employees perceive the developmental opportunities as the key to talent management. But this is practically not the complete truth, as the integrative approach of talent management is the Best Practice.

References:

1. M. Dhanabhakyaam And K. Kokilambal (2014), "A Study On Existing Talent Management Practice And Its Benefits Across Industries"International Journal Of Research In Business Management Vol.2, Issue 7, Pg.No 23-36.
2. Kavitha Rani and Dr. Sanjiv Kumar (2016), "A Study of Problems Encountered By the It Sector In Effective Implementation of Talent Management Practices", Pacific Business Review International Volume 8, Issue 7, January 2016.
3. Dr. Usha Tiwari And Devanshi Shrivastava (2013), "Strategies And Practices Of Talent Management And Their Impact On Employee Retention And Effectiveness" The International Journal Of Managment Vol.2, Issue 4, October 2013.
4. Njeri, K. J. And Orwa, B.H. (2014), "An Empirical Study Of Challenges Affecting Implementation Of Talent Management In The Public Sector In Kenya: A S - Case Of Kenya Broadcasting Corporation", International Journal Of Humanities And Social Science Vol.4, No.7, Pp.217-231
5. Vijay Kumar J., Navaneetha Kumar, R. Nagrajan (2012): The Retention of Employees of MNS Companies of Information Technology. European Jour. Of Social Science Vol. 33 (2) Pp. 230-238
6. Lalitha C. (2012): Managing Employee Attrition-The Hr Role and Challenge. International Jour. Of Research in Management, Economics and Commerce. (Ijrmec). Vol.2 (11) Pp. 262-267.
7. Schwartz, A. (2011). Leadership Development In A Global Environment: Lessons Learned From One Of The World's Largest Employers. Industrial & Commercial Training, 43(1), Pg.No 13-16.
8. [Http://Listz.In/Top-10-It-Companies-In-India.Html#Ixzz4qzwbbv7h](http://Listz.In/Top-10-It-Companies-In-India.Html#Ixzz4qzwbbv7h)